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**WWRF 50 Workshop on Security, Privacy &
Trust Models
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Circular and Sustainable Business Model Innovation
and Development
Future Challenges with Security, privacy and Trustworthiness in
a world of 6G**

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Introduction

Several Horizon Europe projects has laid the foundation for the global communication network of the 2030s by developing the 6G vision and basic concepts, including candidate key technology and business model enablers. These projects address also implementation aspects and challenges of the upcoming 6G platform and encompass

- Use cases, services, and requirements, ensuring the value for society and business.
- Proposing platform and system, ensuring impact on 6G business model innovation and development
- Assuring technology readiness in critical business model and business model ecosystem areas, ensuring businesses strategic autonomy, security, privacy and trust.

Introduction

The agenda is changing today from a Green into a sustainable business model (BM) focus including green, economic and social parameters – “the triple bottom line” approach - combined with the circular approach.

A multi parameter focus – "triple bottom line in a circular perspective" - with parameters that often is difficult to "co optimize" is the new agenda in strategic Multi Business Model Innovation and Development.

This requires a secure and trustworthy platform – without security and trust very little business (Maslows Pyramid).

Triple Bottom Line and the Green, Economic and Social dimension inspired from Rosen's model [28] and Elkington's original model [27]

Vertical Business Model BMES Security and Trust

The vertical - or Vertical Business Model Eco System (VBMES) - of 5G/Beyond 5G (B5G) and 6G as illustrated in figure 1

Figure 1 Vertical BMES

has to operate in this field and now also with security and privacy demands to create trust – a core element for enabling any sustainable business.

The vertical BMES as illustrated in figure 1 can be divided into many diverse use cases among others Energy, Smart Cities and utilities, transportation, automotive, media and entertainment, Agriculture and Agri-food Smart (Air) Ports, E-health and wellness are other examples according to white paper on BMES Ecosystems (1)

This is however a very classical way of characterizing BMES's - and probably an outdated way related to security and privacy.

From Vertical to Horizontal BMES - Security and trust - the impact, challenges

This influence the discussion of security, privacy and trust. As different BM's will have different characteristics of BM dimensions with different value proposition, users and customers, value chain functions, competences, networks, value formulas and relations they will also have different security, privacy and trust models and practices. These has to be integrated.

A mix of security, privacy and trust standards and policies are the new reality – but also the new challenge. How can security, privacy and trust be established in this future 6GBMES?

Figure 2 Horizontal Business Model Ecosystems

Case 1 The Autonomous Car

Autonomous cars and EV cars are some of the hottest topics within the car BMES and wireless technology BMES. 6G will finally realize autonomous cars in a scale up version in the car Business Model ecosystem and will thereby disrupt the car BMES.

The car will become as humans second “home” “carrying all personal data, the same personal values as within today's houses.

However, the access to and use of the car will be very different to what we have seen previous.

Figure 3 Autonomous car with advanced sensors and related BMES

Research Question and methodology

The security and privacy scenarios of future 6G BMES is most interesting to investigate and understand related to 5G and 6G.

- what will be the dominating BMES's of the future 6G BMES be?

and in this context?

- what will be the security, privacy and trust models/practice be?

Case 1 The Autonomous Car

Cars will be personalized cars, which means that everything in the car will be adjusted to the personal use and wellbeing of the person using the car.

Cars will also in greater sense follow a shared business model archetype where the users of cars will not own the car - but share it with others often users not known to each other. Many persons in and out of the car every day, every week, every month ...

Future cars will have numerous sensors and IOT devices embedded and thereby “entrances”

Vehicles will be equipped with software as in very sophisticated machines with the megatrends of connectivity, electrification, and autonomous driving, automotive software content.

Cars will become critical to human life, mobility, security – and trust. With increased software complexity and connectivity - human security and privacy will be put under high threat. Imagine all personal identity are available to anybody, anything when a human enters a car – or even are outside the car. When the human leaves the car it will be possible for anyone that can access the car through one of the technical devices or software to tap into the persons most personal data. With increase AI and quantum computing no one can be safe if some new security and privacy models and solutions are not designed.

Case 2 The CLS Case

CLS is now establishing an energy plant based on garden and parc waste raw material supplement with grass. In the process as sketched in figure 4 the value proposition to be offered will be biofuel, stream for district heating, waste removal (household waste, sludge), removal of biogas plant waste (waste fibers), animal food (grass pills), proteins, biochar, fertilizer amongst others.

Case 2 The CLS Case

In the CLC case we identified 15 Business Model Portfolios, 23 BM's and 7 Businesses involved minimum 18 businesses involved including suppliers and customers.

The manifold of BM's creates many entrances to "the core business" of CLC but also to business and BM's related to CLC. Further someone who would like to enter can access through several of the BM's dimensions competence, users and customers, network and relations.

This sets CLC in a extremely challenging situation related to security and privacy.

Case 3 Symbiosis Network Applications - — “The Business Network Approach”

Symbiosis networks like Kalundborg and Sotånæs Industrial Symbiosis together with Greenlab Skive and Greenporth North is "a network application" that "facilitates" different businesses within a limited area so the businesses can operate together as seen in examples for Sotånæs Symbiosis Center and Greenlab figure 5 and figure 6.

Sotånæs Symbiosis Network

Pictures of parts of SSN in 2018 and 2022 (Smögenlax, 2018)

Figure 5 Sotånæs Industrial Symbiosis, Sweden

Case 3 Symbiosis Network Applications - — “The Business Network Approach”

Greenlab Skive

Greenlab Skive from a vision in 2016 to reality in 2022

GS's vision is to transform the way green energy is produced, converted, stored, and applied, and purpose to act like a testbed for theories in practice and look for viable green solutions to the world's biggest challenges.

Figure 6 Greenlab Symbiosis Center, Denmark

Figure 5 Sotånäs Industrial Symbiosis, Sweden

Case 3 Symbiosis Network Applications - – “The Business Network Approach”

The Symbiosis Centers BMES creates a variety of BM's - biofuel, district heating, removal of waste, animal food, proteins, algae for cosmetics or solar Cellar coating, biofuel and Co2 reduction.

The Symbiosis networks have in a limited geographical area several businesses, BM's related and operating.

The number of businesses and BM's varies from one Symbiosis network to another – they are like a horizontal BMES. Most businesses in the Symbiosis network are fixed and stays in the Symbiosis Center for a longer time due to heavy investments in physical equipment and construction within the symbiosis network.

Several of the businesses are heavily interrelated and depend on each other as one business waste could be raw material to another business.

This gives several security and privacy issues.

Reflection and discussion

The 5G, 5G and Beyond (B5G) or 6G increases the security and privacy challenge as more businesses, business networks and Symbiosis Business Network becomes more open, more related and operates with higher speed. AI and Quantum computing will add even more to these security challenges.

Many of the businesses BM's are and will be heavily embedded with IOT and advance sensors that can be accessed from outside. Data from these will be used for monitoring, analytical purposes, scenarios, digital twin formation and many more things.

Future verticals embedded with 6G technology - or 6G BMES+ s - will have more horizontals - which will form BM's that are not from the same origin and with the same security rullset and software

Future business will demand more open network under security – which initially seems as a dilemma. How can You do openness and security at the same time. The openness issue is required on behalf of the need for fast, dynamic and agile BMI and operation to cope with tomorrows increasing demands for change and new BM's.

Reflection and discussion

Future business will require the possibility to connect with anybody, anything, anytime and anywhere. This push the API and Security software of tomorrows 6G BMES.

Different network constellations that are more horizontal BMES based push increasing number of BM's to be able to connect, relate and capture values from anybody, anything, anytime and anywhere.

As security issues increase the trust elements – a fundamental “culture” to enable value exchange between businesses will be challenged

Solutions ... are difficult so see at the point ww stand right now.

This will highly influence future security and privacy setup and software development

The big question is will we ever be secure and be able to have privacy?

Conclusion

The Sustainable Business Model Innovation and development are challenged by:

- ✓ New Business Models and Changed Business Models will challenge existing security systems and regulations and calls for new systems and regulations.
- ✓ Increased advanced AI, digitalization, sensor and measurement technologies will add to this mentioned fact.
- ✓ Increase in Network Based and Shared Business Models and Business Model Innovation and Development makes it even more difficult to secure the BMES and comply to the regulations of Privacy and GDPR
- ✓ Increased Circular Green BM competence innovation and development – requires advanced security
- ✓ Increased Collaboration on Research, Innovation and development of security and privacy in a world of 6G is needed.

Further research - Strategic GBMI - Privacy - GDPR

How can strategic GBMI contribute to further research on Privacy and GDPR in different fields of Green Business Modelling, offering future research directions of Privacy and GDPR.

The research on Privacy and GDPR will be continued in the next Greenbizz project – Greenbizz II. In this project starting at 1.1.2023 the circular and entire value network will be included which will address questions - How to meet Privacy and GDPR regulations across different businesses in a timely and cost efficient way.

Questions

Green Multi Business Model and Technology Innovation
– with Humans and/or Things?

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